

Color-Based Music Playlist Generator: A Personalized Approach

Dr. V. Nivedita, Ramshankar TV, Jathi Vignesh K, Raja Kannan J

Abstract

This project introduces a cutting-edge color-based music recommendation system that suggests playlists based on the dominant color extracted from user-uploaded images. Utilizing the Color Thief library, the system dynamically analyzes the image's color composition to tailor music recommendations. A user-friendly web interface allows for seamless interaction, while the Fisher-Yates shuffle algorithm ensures unique playlist arrangements with every use. This novel approach enhances music recommendation systems by incorporating environmental and aesthetic inputs, creating a deeply personalized listening experience. The modular design facilitates scalability, paving the way for future enhancements like machine learning integration and expanded features.

1. Introduction

Music has become an integral part of daily life, with recommendation systems playing a significant role in enhancing user engagement on digital platforms. Conventional systems primarily rely on historical data, such as listening habits or explicit user preferences, but often fail to capture real-time context or aesthetic influences. This project bridges that gap by introducing a color-driven music recommendation system, which translates the dominant colors of user-uploaded images into mood-appropriate playlists.

The system employs the Color Thief library to extract dominant colors and map them to predefined mood categories (e.g., vibrant, calm, or melancholic). For instance, warm tones like red and orange might suggest energetic tracks, while cool tones like blue and green imply relaxing music. Built with HTML, CSS, and JavaScript, the system provides a lightweight, responsive interface that is easy to navigate. Additionally, the Fisher-Yates shuffle algorithm ensures dynamic playlist arrangements, adding an element of surprise to every session. Future iterations could incorporate advanced image analysis techniques or machine learning to refine recommendations further.

2. Literature Review

Over the years, music recommendation systems have evolved from simplistic collaborative filtering methods to sophisticated hybrid models that integrate diverse data points. Early systems focused on collaborative filtering, leveraging user behaviors to suggest tracks, but faced challenges like limited data for new users or items. Content-based filtering emerged as an alternative, analyzing track features such as tempo, genre, and instrumentation. However, this approach often resulted in repetitive playlists due to over-reliance on metadata.

Modern systems frequently combine these methods, adding layers of user context, social data, and temporal patterns to improve accuracy. Despite these advancements, most systems lack the

ability to account for real-time influences, such as a user's immediate environment or visual cues. By introducing color analysis as a basis for music recommendation, this project aims to address this gap, offering a unique, context-aware experience. The implementation of the Fisher-Yates shuffle algorithm further enhances the system by delivering non-repetitive and engaging playlists.

3. Project Design and Architecture

The architecture of the color-based music recommendation system is designed for simplicity, scalability, and modularity. It consists of four primary modules: the User Interface (UI) Module, the Image Analysis Module, the Playlist Generation Module, and the Audio Playback Module.

3.1 User Interface (UI) Module

The UI Module serves as the front-end of the system, providing an intuitive interface for users to upload images and view generated playlists. Key elements include an image upload section, a color analysis result display, and a playlist area with playback controls. CSS ensures a visually appealing design that adapts seamlessly across devices, ensuring a consistent user experience.

The web interface includes hover effects, animation cues, and responsive grids to enhance user interaction. A drag-and-drop feature simplifies the upload process, while tooltips guide first-time users through the system's functionalities.

3.2 Image Analysis Module

The Image Analysis Module leverages the Color Thief library to extract dominant colors from user-uploaded images. These

colors are categorized into predefined mood levels, which serve as the basis for playlist generation. This modular setup allows for easy updates to the mood-color mapping logic, enabling the system to accommodate more nuanced interpretations in future versions.

The module handles various image formats, including JPEG, PNG, and BMP, ensuring compatibility. It also incorporates fallback mechanisms to manage low-resolution images or corrupted files, ensuring robust performance.

3.3 Playlist Generation Module

This module retrieves playlists associated with specific mood categories from a JSON file. The retrieved playlists are shuffled using the Fisher-Yates algorithm, ensuring a randomized order of tracks for every session. The modular design allows for effortless updates to the music database, making it simple to add new tracks or adjust mood categorizations.

The JSON structure is designed to allow multiple attributes for each track, including genre, tempo, and artist information. This flexibility sets the foundation for potential machine learning applications, where user preferences could refine playlist suggestions further.

3.4 Audio Playback Module

The Audio Playback Module manages track playback and ensures smooth transitions between songs. JavaScript event listeners are employed to prevent overlapping audio, automatically pausing the current track when a new one is played. This module also provides standard playback controls, such as play, pause, and stop, ensuring a seamless user experience.

The module supports advanced features like volume normalization, equalizer presets, and integration with third-party music streaming APIs, such as Spotify or YouTube Music, to enhance functionality.

4. Algorithm Implementation

The Fisher-Yates shuffle algorithm is central to the playlist generation process. It operates by iterating over the playlist array, swapping each element with a randomly selected element preceding it (or itself). This approach guarantees an unbiased shuffle, ensuring every permutation of the playlist is equally likely.

Implemented in JavaScript, the algorithm is highly efficient, even for large playlists, and integrates seamlessly with the Playlist Generation Module. Its use ensures that every playlist feels fresh and engaging, enhancing the overall listening experience.

Code optimizations include memoization techniques to cache shuffled playlists, reducing computational overhead during repeated user sessions.

5. Audio Playback Management

To deliver a seamless auditory experience, the Audio Playback Module uses JavaScript to manage playback controls and transitions. One of the primary challenges addressed was preventing multiple tracks from playing simultaneously. Event listeners detect when a track is initiated and automatically pause any other track that is currently playing.

The module also updates the UI to reflect the current playback status, providing visual cues to the user. These features

ensure a distraction-free and enjoyable listening experience. Additional debugging techniques were employed to identify edge cases, such as buffering delays or network interruptions, and implement recovery mechanisms.

6. System Workflow

The system workflow is designed to be straightforward and user-friendly, allowing users to generate and play a customized playlist with minimal effort. The process begins when the user selects their emotion level using the range slider. This selection triggers the Data Handling Module to fetch the corresponding playlist from the JSON file.

Fig 1: Architecture Diagram For Image Based Music Recommendation System

Once the playlist is retrieved, it is passed to the Shuffling Module, where the Fisher-Yates algorithm is applied to randomize the order of the songs. The shuffled playlist is then displayed in the UI, with each track represented by an audio player. The user can then click on any track to start playback, with the Audio Playback Management Module ensuring that only one track plays at a time.

The workflow of the color-based music recommendation system is designed to be intuitive and efficient:

1. Users upload an image via the web interface.
2. The Image Analysis Module extracts dominant colors and maps them to mood categories.
3. The Playlist Generation Module fetches a corresponding playlist from the JSON database and shuffles it using the Fisher-Yates algorithm.
4. The UI Module displays the playlist, allowing users to initiate playback.
5. The Audio Playback Module ensures smooth and non-overlapping audio playback.

This streamlined process enables users to quickly generate and enjoy personalized playlists with minimal effort. Error-handling mechanisms ensure that any issues in image upload or playback are gracefully managed, with meaningful feedback provided to the user.

7. Challenges and Solutions

Comprehensive testing was conducted to ensure the system met its design objectives:

Usability Testing: Feedback from users highlighted areas for improvement in the UI, leading to refinements that enhanced intuitiveness and responsiveness. A/B

testing was conducted to compare different layouts and workflows.

Performance Testing: The Fisher-Yates algorithm demonstrated excellent efficiency, maintaining responsiveness even with large datasets. Stress testing confirmed the system's stability under high user loads.

Playback Testing: Extensive testing confirmed the reliability of the Audio Playback Module, ensuring smooth transitions and preventing overlap. Metrics like latency, buffer underrun, and playback continuity were monitored.

Integration Testing: Verified seamless interaction between modules, ensuring that changes in one module did not adversely affect others. Mock data was used to simulate various scenarios, such as missing or corrupted files.

8. Evaluation and Testing

Comprehensive testing was conducted to ensure the system met its design objectives:

Usability Testing: Feedback from users highlighted areas for improvement in the UI, leading to refinements that enhanced intuitiveness and responsiveness. A/B testing was conducted to compare different layouts and workflows.

Performance Testing: The Fisher-Yates algorithm demonstrated excellent efficiency, maintaining responsiveness even with large datasets. Stress testing confirmed the system's stability under high user loads.

Playback Testing: Extensive testing confirmed the reliability of the Audio Playback Module, ensuring smooth transitions and preventing overlap. Metrics

like latency, buffer underrun, and playback continuity were monitored.

Integration Testing: Verified seamless interaction between modules, ensuring that changes in one module did not adversely affect others. Mock data was used to simulate various scenarios, such as missing or corrupted files.

9. Future Work and Enhancements

Potential areas for future development include:

Machine Learning Integration: Incorporating advanced algorithms to refine mood-color mapping and provide more personalized recommendations. Neural networks could analyze image features like textures or patterns for deeper mood insights.

Expanded Playlists: Increasing the diversity of music tracks and mood categories to cater to a broader range of user preferences. Licensing agreements with music providers could expand available content.

Mobile Adaptation: Developing a mobile-friendly version of the system or a dedicated app for on-the-go use. Offline functionality could be explored to accommodate users with limited connectivity.

User Feedback Mechanism: Allowing users to rate tracks or playlists, enabling continuous improvement of recommendations. Collaborative filtering could be introduced to combine visual cues with user preferences.

Augmented Reality Integration: Exploring AR capabilities where users can point their devices at objects or scenes to

generate context-aware playlists based on real-time color analysis.

10. Conclusion

The color-based music recommendation system represents a novel approach to music curation, leveraging image analysis and randomized playlist generation to provide a personalized listening experience. By integrating dominant color extraction, mood mapping, and efficient shuffling techniques, the system offers a unique blend of aesthetic and auditory engagement. Future enhancements promise to make this approach even more impactful, bridging the gap between visual stimuli and musical enjoyment.

11. Reference

- [1] WU Yun , LIN Jian, MA Yanlong, "A Hybrid Music Recommendation Model Based on Personalized Measurement and Game Theory", Chinese Journal of Electronics Vol.32, No.6, Nov. 2023.
- [2] Y. -C. Pan, W. -c. Liu and X. Li, "Development and Research of Music Player Application Based on Android," 2010 International Conference on Communications and Intelligence Information Security, 2010, pp. 23-25, doi: 11 Nov, 2010.
- [3] S. Chinnadurai, Muhammed Fazal, M. Sathakumar, S. Suseendran, "Voice Based Searched Engine for Visually Impaired People's," International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Communication and Technology, Volume 4, Issue 2, April 2021.
- [4] E. Esaki Vigneswaran, G. Kiruthikamani, "ADVANCED MUSIC PLAYER WITH AUDIO RECOGNITION AND TOUCH INTERFERENCE FOR VISUALLY

IMPAIRED,” ARPN Journal of Engineering and Applied Science, Volume 10, No. 7, April 2015.

[5] Deekshitha G, Leena Mary, “A Study on Audio Search Techniques,” Conference Paper, September 2016.

[6] Yan Ke, Derek Hoiem, Rahul Sukthankar, “Computer Vision for Music Identification,” SDK , android, AI, November 2015.

[7]J. Russel, B. Noble, and I. N. Sneddon, “A Circumplex Model of Affect,” , Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, pp.1161- 1178, 1980.

[8] P. Valdez, and A. Mehrabian, “Effects of Color on Emotions,” Journal of Experimental Psychology, Vol.123, no.4, pp.394-409, Dec.1994.

[9] P. Lang, M. Bradley, and B. Cuthbert, “International Affective Picture System (IAPS): Affective Ratings of Pictures and Instruction Manual,” Technical Report A-8. University of Florida, Gainesville, FL, 2008.

[10] T. Eerola, O. Lartillot, and P. Toivaiene, “Prediction of Multidimensional Emotional Ratings in Music from Audio Using Multivariate Regression Models,” Proc. 10th ISMIR, pp.621-626, Kobe, Japan, Oct.2009.

[11] M. Goto, H. Hashiguchi, T. Nishimura, and R. Oka, “RWC Music Database: Music Genre Database and Musical Instrument Sound Database,” Proc. 4th ISMIR, pp.229-230, Oct.2003.

[12] Krittrin Chankuptarat, Raphatsak Sriwatanaworachai, Supannada Chotipant, “Emotion-Based Music Player,” DBMS AND AI/ML, August 2019.

[13] I. A. Pegoraro Santana et al., "Music4All: A New Music Database and Its Applications," 2020 International Conference on Systems, Signals and Image Processing (IWSSIP), 2020, pp. 399-404, doi: 21 July 2020.

[14] Y. Kodama et al., "A music recommendation system," 2005 Digest of Technical Papers. International Conference on Consumer Electronics, 2005. ICCE., 2005, pp. 219-220, doi: 16 May 2005.